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Detecting Sybil Attacks in Clustered Wireless Sensor Networks Based on Energy Trust System (ETS) §

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1 **Abstract:** Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are an emerging technology used in many applications
 2 in both the civilian and military domains. Typically, these networks are deployed in remote and
 3 hostile environments. They are vulnerable to various kinds of security attacks, of which sybil attacks
 4 are some of the most harmful. Thus, it is necessary to solve the problems related to sensor node
 5 constraints and the need for high WSN security. This paper proposes an energy trust system (ETS)
 6 for WSNs to effectively detect sybil attacks. It employs multi-level detection based on identity and
 7 position verification. Then, a trust algorithm is applied based on the energy of each sensor node.
 8 Data aggregation is also utilized to reduce communication overhead and save energy. We analyze
 9 the performance of the proposed system in terms of security and resource consumption using
 10 theoretical and simulation-based approaches. The simulation results show that the proposed ETS is
 11 effective and robust in detecting sybil attacks in terms of the true and false positive rates. By virtue
 12 of the application of multi-level detection, the proposed system achieves more than 70% detection
 13 at the first level, which significantly increases to 100% detection at the second level. Furthermore,
 14 this system reduces communication overhead, memory overhead, and energy consumption by
 15 eliminating the exchange of feedback and recommendation messages among sensor nodes.

16 **Keywords:** energy; trust; detection; sybil attack; wireless sensor network.

17 **PACS:** J0101

18 1. Introduction

19 A wireless sensor network (WSN) consists of a large number of distributed autonomous sensors
 20 that cooperatively monitor physical or environmental characteristics, such as sound, vibration,
 21 temperature, pressure, motion or pollutants, and send their readings to a central node such as a base
 22 station (BS) [1][2]. WSNs are used in many applications, including health-care applications, battlefield
 23 surveillance, and environmental and habitat monitoring [3]. Typically, sensor nodes are deployed
 24 in remote and hostile environments [4], and they are generally not equipped with tamper-resistant
 25 hardware [5]. WSNs are vulnerable to various attacks because of their wireless and distributed nature
 26 [6]. The sensor nodes are subject to constraints on various resources, such as memory, computing
 27 capability, and energy, which make security solutions more challenging to implement in WSNs
 28 [4][7]. Sybil attacks are considered one of the most harmful types of attacks in WSNs because they

29 serve as a gateway to other attacks, such as attacks on routing, voting, fair resource allocation, data
 30 aggregation, distributed storage, and misbehaviour detection. A sybil attack occurs when a malicious
 31 node illegitimately claims to have multiple identities by creating new identities or impersonating
 32 existing ones [8]. Therefore, the ability to detect sybil attacks is important in WSNs. Many solutions
 33 have been proposed for the detection of sybil attacks, such as radio resource testing, random key
 34 pre-distribution, registration of node identities, and position verification [3]. However, there is no
 35 universally acceptable security solution that can completely counter sybil attacks [9]. These security
 36 mechanisms remain inadequate because of their high computational cost and the resource constraints
 37 of WSNs. Furthermore, because of the unattended deployment of sensor networks and the nature
 38 of sybil attacks, these security solutions address only part of the problem. Recently, trust-based
 39 approaches have emerged as an important security paradigm in WSNs [10]. When a sensor node
 40 is compromised, security mechanisms such as authentication and cryptography cannot overcome
 41 the problem. Hence, a trust mechanism improves network security by continuously observing node
 42 behaviour/performance to evaluate the trustworthiness of the nodes [5]. This approach is regarded
 43 as a security solution that combines high security performance with low resource consumption [6].
 44 In this paper, we propose an energy trust system (ETS) in which a multi-level approach is applied to
 45 detect sybil attacks in clustered WSNs. Each group of nodes forms a cluster, and these clusters are
 46 used as fusion points for the aggregation of data to the base station, which reduces communication
 47 overhead and allows for scalability [11]. Furthermore, this approach eliminates the exchange of
 48 feedback and recommendation messages between nodes at the same level or at different levels.
 49 Thus, the proposed ETS is a light mechanism because of the clustering of the network, utilizing
 50 an aggregation mechanism, and the elimination of feedback and recommendation exchange among
 51 nodes. Figure 1 illustrates the mechanism of a sybil attack in a clustered WSN. Here, the system
 52 comprises three types of entities: cluster members (CMs), cluster heads (CHs), and a base station
 53 (BS). Each CM sends its data to the corresponding CH, and the CHs then aggregate, process, and
 54 forward these data to the BS. In a sybil attack, a malicious node communicates with a legitimate
 55 node and obtains information on that node, such as its identity and position. Then, by using this
 56 information, the attacker can create identities of the same type to launch attacks on legitimate nodes
 57 in the network [12].

Figure 1. Model of a sybil attack in a WSN.

58 The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly describes the related work
 59 addressing energy trust systems for WSNs. Section 3 introduces the proposed ETS model for WSNs.

60 Sections 4 presents theoretical and simulation-based analyses and evaluations of ETS. Section 5
61 concludes this paper and outlines possible future directions of research.

62 2. Related Work

63 Intrusion detection systems are regarded as a last defence against attacker nodes in WSNs.
64 Trust-based intrusion detection has become increasingly important because of its ability to counter
65 attacks on sensor nodes [13]. In the literature, trust is defined as a bond of reliance and confidence
66 with other sensor nodes in the network, which establishes a basis for future behaviour. A sensor
67 node is able to predict the behaviour of its surrounding nodes and maintains certain expectations
68 regarding what they will not do [6]. Existing trust detection systems typically discover intruder
69 nodes based on experience of past interactions [13]. Chen et al. [14] proposed ATSN, a distributed
70 agent-based trust management scheme for WSNs. It uses agent nodes to monitor the behaviour of
71 nodes within their radio ranges and broadcast their trust ratings. However, although ATSN can
72 counter certain attacks, such as bad-mouthing and on – off attacks, it cannot overcome sybil attacks
73 [15]. Ishmanov et al. [16] proposed TE, a trust management scheme for WSNs. In this scheme, each
74 node evaluates the trust of nodes within its communication range by observing them and evaluating
75 their trust values based on their misbehaviour weights. However, TE cannot detect attacks with a
76 low percentage of bad behaviour [17].

77 In WSNs, node clustering is an effective topology for improved network control and supports
78 scalability to networks consisting of hundreds or thousands of nodes. Hierarchical clustering is an
79 important scheme that aids in reducing energy consumption and increasing a network's lifetime
80 [18][19][20][21]. However, very few trust management systems have been designed for clustered
81 WSNs [18], including GTMS [22], LDTS [18], and HTMP [13]. Shaikh et al. [22] proposed GTMS,
82 a group-based trust management scheme for clustered WSNs. It evaluates trust based on past
83 experience of interactions in message delivery. However, the system requires direct observations
84 or recommendations from other nodes and therefore consumes a significant amount of energy and
85 resources [23][24]. Li et al. [18] introduced LDTS, a dependable trust system for clustered WSNs. This
86 system considers the identities of the sensor nodes. Each node calculates trust based on both direct
87 trust measures (observations) and indirect trust measures (recommendations). Trust is evaluated
88 based on the numbers of successful and unsuccessful interactions within a certain threshold time.
89 However, the gathering of recommendations requires node-to-node communication, which increases
90 the energy consumption.

91 Energy is an essential parameter in WSNs because its availability is extremely constraint in sensor
92 nodes [13]. Furthermore, energy consumption is a vital issue in the design of intrusion detection
93 systems (IDSs) [25]. Therefore, a new class of trust detection systems based on energy has been
94 proposed for WSNs. Bao et al. [13] presented HTMP, a hierarchical trust management protocol for
95 clustered WSNs. This scheme considers two social trust components, namely, intimacy and honesty,
96 and two quality-of-service trust components, namely, energy and unselfishness, for calculating trust.
97 It relies on a probability model that utilizes a stochastic Petri net approach to analyse the protocol's
98 performance and validates the subjective trust against an objective trust obtained based on the
99 ground-truth node status. However, applying such a complex trust system at each cluster member
100 and cluster head is unrealistic [26]. Han et al. [27] presented IDSEP, an intrusion detection scheme
101 for clustered WSNs based on energy prediction. It identifies malicious nodes based on abnormal
102 energy consumption. However, in this algorithm, the sensor nodes consume a large amount of
103 energy [28]. Muraleedharan et al. [29] introduced a hybrid intelligence approach for the detection
104 of sybil attacks in WSNs. Their system combines the Bayesian algorithm with swarm intelligence. It
105 employs a swarm intelligence algorithm to collect the information regarding each route and detect
106 malicious nodes based on their variations in energy [30]. However, this system requires the collection
107 of information on each route, which results in communication overhead.

108 The schemes mentioned above have various limitations; for example, these approaches do not satisfy

109 the resource constraints of WSNs and, more specifically, those related to large-scale WSNs and the
110 nature of sybil attacks. However, trust systems for WSNs remain an open and challenging topic [31].
111 To overcome the limitations of the systems proposed to date, we introduces a lightweight trust system
112 called ETS, which is based on energy as a threshold parameter, to counter sybil attacks in clustered
113 WSNs. It applies multi-level detection in a hierarchical topology. At each level of detection, identity
114 and position verification is applied to each sensor node in the network. The proposed ETS also
115 utilizes a data aggregation mechanism to reduce communication overhead and energy consumption
116 [32]. Furthermore, ETS eliminates the exchange of recommendations among nodes in the network,
117 thereby significantly increasing the system efficiency and reducing the effects of malicious nodes
118 [18]. This elimination of recommendation exchange also reduces the memory, communication, and
119 energy required to implement the proposed scheme. This paper presents both simulation-based and
120 analytical results. Moreover, ETS uses a timing window mechanism, which is also used in ET [16],
121 GTMS [22], and LDTS [18], to reduce the effect of time on trust values and to better resist sybil attacks.
122

123 3. Proposed Energy Trust System Method

124 3.1. Network Topology and Assumptions

125 Our goal is to develop a lightweight trust-based system with a multi-level detection mechanism
126 to eliminate sybil attacks in clustered WSNs. The establishment and management of a trust
127 detection system in a hierarchical and clustered topology have many advantages, such as reducing
128 communication overhead and energy consumption, facilitating data aggregation, and improving
129 network scalability and throughput [18], [21], [25], [33]. We assume that the network is a
130 homogeneous WSN consisting of N sensor nodes. The network includes three types of entities: a
131 base station (BS), cluster heads (CHs), and cluster members (CMs). The BS is a central command
132 authority. It is assumed that the BS is trustworthy and cannot be compromised by an attacker and
133 that it is not subject to any resource constraints. The CMs and CHs are within the communication
134 range of the BS. We also assume that the CHs have more power than the CMs. Each CH is responsible
135 for the CMs in its cluster. The network is based on single-hop networking, in which each node uses
136 single-hop communication to reach its corresponding monitoring node (CH or BS), which has a fixed
137 position for each node. Algorithms such as EC [34], EEHC [20], HEED [21], and LEACH [35] are used
138 to cluster the WSN and to select the CH for each cluster at run time, for which purpose they consider
139 the balance between the amount of energy consumed and the functionality of the CH. A class-based
140 addressing scheme is used, such as that presented in [36], in which each node is uniquely identified
141 by a triplet of the form <location, node type, node subtype>. However, the selection of the CHs and
142 the addressing scheme are out of the scope of this work. Figure 2 illustrates the ETS network topology.

Figure 2. Network topology.

143 3.2. Energy Trust System (ETS) Method

144 The proposed system is based on a three-level hierarchical WSN topology, as explained below:

145 1. CM level

146 Each CM sends its data to its corresponding CH, accompanied by its identity in the form $\langle \text{ID},$
 147 Position, $E_t \rangle$, at an assigned time. Each node has a unique ID and static position. E_t is updated
 148 with every message sent to the CH and is calculated as follows:

$$E_t = (E_{consumed} + E_{residual}) \quad (1)$$

$$E_{consumed} = \sum(E_{state}) = E_T + E_R + E_S + E_{switching} \quad (2)$$

149 where E_{state} is the energy consumed by the CM in each state (transmitting, receiving, sleeping,
 150 and switching); E_T , E_R , E_S , and $E_{switching}$ are the amounts of energy consumed in the transmitting,
 151 receiving, sleeping, and switching states, respectively; and $E_{residual}$ is the residual energy available
 152 in the CM.

153 154 2. CH level

155 The 1st level of detection is applied at the CH level. The clustering of sensor nodes is an effective
 156 means of topology control [21]. Each CH is responsible for the nodes in its cluster. Each CH keeps
 157 a record (as a matrix) of the IDs and positions of the CMs as follows:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} ID_1 & X_1 & Y_1 \\ ID_2 & X_2 & Y_2 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ ID_{n-1} & X_{n-1} & Y_{n-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

158 where C is the matrix for each cluster head that represents the IDs and positions of its cluster
 159 members and n represents the number of nodes in the cluster, including the cluster head.
 160 Furthermore, each cluster head maintains an array representing the energy values E for each
 161 cluster member and updates it with the arrival of every message from the nodes, as shown below:

162

$$E_{n-1} = \left(E_1 \ E_2 \ \dots \ E_{n-1} \right) \quad (4)$$

Whenever a CH receives a message from one of its sensors, it applies the ETS scheme, using verification and trust mechanisms to check the source of that message. It then aggregates and forwards the data to the BS as follows:

- (a) Checking: The CH checks the ID and position of the sender of the received message. If the node is a member of its cluster, then the next step of detection, namely, trust calculation, is initiated. Otherwise, the message is deleted. The purpose of this step is to detect a sybil attack with a forged ID and position. The purpose of the trust calculation step is to detect the worst-case scenario of a sybil attack in which the attacker succeeds in impersonating the ID and position of a legitimate node.
- (b) Trust calculation: The energy of the sensor node is checked against a threshold parameter in this step. The CH checks E_t as follows:

$$E \geq \sum(E_t + \lambda 1) \quad (5)$$

where E is the energy value saved in the matrix maintained by the CH and $\lambda 1$ is the rate of energy variation. When $(E \geq E_t + \lambda 1)$, the number of successful interactions S is increased, whereas otherwise, the number of unsuccessful interactions U is increased, as follows:

$$E = \begin{cases} \geq E_t + \lambda 1, & \text{increase successful interaction count (S)} \\ < E_t + \lambda 1, & \text{increase unsuccessful interaction count (U)} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The trust $T_{ch,x}$ is evaluated as in the following equation:

$$T_{ch,x}(\Delta t) = \left\lceil \left(\frac{10 * S_{ch,x}(\Delta t)}{S_{ch,x}(\Delta t) + U_{ch,x}(\Delta t)} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{U_{ch,x}(\Delta t)}} \right) \right\rceil \quad (7)$$

where $S_{ch,x}$ is the total number of successful interactions of the CH with node x during the time window Δt , $U_{ch,x}$ is the total number of unsuccessful interactions of the CH with node x during the time window Δt , and $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ is the nearest integer function. The CH evaluates the trust value as an unsigned integer in the range of $[0, 10]$, where a value of 10 indicates complete trust.

In [22] and [18], the timing window Δt was introduced as the basis for determining the number of successful and unsuccessful interactions. Some number of slides are applied to this window depending on the scenario. In this work, a timing window with one slide is used to count the numbers of successful and unsuccessful interactions with the nodes based on the results of Equation 5. Each CH stores the timing windows, in matrix form, to act as a history for each node. The length of the timing window can be shorter or longer depending on the scenario. As time progresses, the window shifts to omit the oldest interactions while adding newer ones.

Figure 3 illustrates the timing window Δt . Furthermore, the expression $\frac{1}{\sqrt{U_{ch,x}}}$ from Equation 7, which is considered as a strict punishment factor for unsuccessful interactions, rapidly approaches 0 with an increasing number of unsuccessful interactions $U_{ch,x}$.

- (c) Aggregation: The CH waits to receive the data from all nodes in its cluster. It then aggregates and forwards the collected data to the BS, accompanied by the $\langle \text{ID}, \text{Position}, E_t \rangle$ triplet for the sending CH, at a specified time.

Figure 3. Timing window Δt .

Algorithm 1: Cluster head-based (1st level detection)

Input: Check whether the message was sent from a legitimate or sybil node.

Output: Identification of a sybil attack in a WSN by applying the ETS.

- (a) Initialize the sensor nodes.
- (b) CH receives a message from a CM.
- (c) CH initializes verification (ID, position, E) of the sender.
- (d) **If** legal (ID & position)
- (e) **If** ($E \geq E_t + \lambda 1$), **then**
- (f) S^{++}
- (g) **Else**
- (h) U^{++}
- (i) Calculate trust based on Equation 7.
- (j) **While** ($T \geq 5$)
- (k) Aggregate ($n-1$) data & send to BS.
- (l) **Else**
- (m) Delete received message (sybil attack).
- (n) **End**

3. BS level

The 2nd level of detection is applied at the BS level. The BS is the central command authority. The amount of data that are actually transmitted to the BS is reduced by clustering the network. The BS monitors the CHs in the network. As is done by the CHs, the BS saves the IDs and positions of the CHs in a matrix B , as follows:

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} ID_1 & X_1 & Y_1 \\ ID_2 & X_2 & Y_2 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ ID_m & X_m & Y_m \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where m represents the number of CHs in the network. The energy value E of each CH is also saved in an array at the BS and updated with the arrival of every message from a CH, as shown in Equation 9:

$$E_m = \left(E_1 \quad E_2 \quad \dots \quad E_m \right) \quad (9)$$

228 The BS applies the ETS method when a message arrives from a CH as follows:
229

- 230 (a) Checking: The BS verifies the ID and position of the sender of the received message. Then,
231 the trust calculation step is initialized if the sender is an authentic CH. Otherwise, the
232 message is deleted.
233 (b) Trust calculation: The calculation performed in this step is based on the energy of the CHs.
234 The BS checks E_t as follows:

$$E \geq \sum(E_t + \lambda 2) \quad (10)$$

235 where E is the energy value saved in the matrix maintained by the BS and $\lambda 2$ is the rate of
236 energy variation.

237 When ($E \geq E_t + \lambda 2$), the number of successful interactions S is increased, whereas
238 otherwise, the number of unsuccessful interactions U is increased, as follows:
239

$$E = \begin{cases} \geq E_t + \lambda 2, & \text{increase successful interaction count } (S) \\ < E_t + \lambda 2, & \text{increase unsuccessful interaction count } (U) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

240 The BS evaluates the trust value $R_{bs,ch}$ as follows:

$$R_{bs,ch}(\Delta t) = \left[\left(\frac{10 * S_{bs,ch}(\Delta t)}{S_{bs,ch}(\Delta t) + U_{bs,ch}(\Delta t)} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{U_{bs,ch}(\Delta t)}} \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

241 where $S_{bs,ch}$ and $U_{bs,ch}$ represent the total numbers of successful and unsuccessful
242 interactions, respectively, of the BS with cluster head ch during the time window Δt and $[\cdot]$
243 is the nearest integer function. The BS evaluates the trust value as an unsigned integer in the
244 range of $[0, 10]$, where a value of 10 indicates complete trust.

245 One slide of the timing window Δt is applied to count the numbers of successful and
246 unsuccessful interactions with the nodes based on the results of Equation 10. The timing
247 windows Δt are saved by the base station in matrix form to serve as a history for each
248 cluster. The length of the timing window is decided depending on the scenario. As time
249 progresses, the window shifts to omit the oldest interactions while adding newer ones.
250

251 **Algorithm 2:** Base station-based (2^{nd} level detection)

252 **Input:** Check whether the message was sent from a legitimate or sybil node.

253 **Output:** Identify a sybil attack in a WSN by applying ETS.
254

- 255 (a) Initialize sensor nodes.
256 (b) BS receives a message from a CH.
257 (c) BS initializes verification (ID, position, E) of the sender.
258 (d) **If** legal (ID & position)
259 (e) **If** ($E \geq E_t + \lambda 2$), **then**
260 (f) S^{++}
261 (g) **Else**
262 (h) U^{++}
263 (i) Calculate trust (R) based on Equation 12.
264 (j) **If** ($R \geq 5$)
265 (k) Accept data.
266 (l) **Else**
267 (m) Delete received message (sybil attack).
268 (n) **End**
269

270 4. Performance Evaluation

271 In this section, we present the results of our evaluation and comparison of the proposed ETS
 272 scheme against existing schemes. An OMNeT++ simulation and the MiXiM framework were used
 273 to simulate multi-level detection in a clustered WSN. The detection accuracy of the ETS approach
 274 was evaluated in terms of the true and false positive rates. Furthermore, the energy consumption
 275 of ETS was also calculated. Moreover, theoretical comparisons with well-known existing trust
 276 systems, namely, LDTS [18] and GTMS [22], were performed in terms of communication and memory
 277 overhead. Table 1 reports the parameters used to simulate the system.

Table 1. ETS simulation parameters.

Parameter	Value
Simulation time	1200 s
Network size	500 m x 500 m
Carrier frequency	2.4 GHz
Max TXPower	1.1 mW
Number of nodes	varies (from 10 to 46, depending on the simulation)
Number of sybils	varies (from 2 to 20, depending on the simulation)

278 4.1. Detection Accuracy

279 The reliability and the level of security of the proposed ETS were evaluated based on the
 280 probability of accurate detection of the sybil nodes. A true positive corresponds to an accurate
 281 detection of a sybil attack, whereas as incorrect detection is known as a false positive.

Figure 4. Detection accuracy.

282 The detection accuracy of the proposed ETS was found to be greater than 70%, with significantly
 283 fewer false positives at the first level of detection (the CH level), as demonstrated in Figure 4. This
 284 figure also shows that the detection accuracy of the proposed system increases at the second level
 285 of detection (the BS level) to reach 100%. The reason for this increase is that the workload on the
 286 cluster heads causes rapid changes in their energy values, making it very difficult for a sybil node
 287 to correctly falsify the necessary value even when the sybil successfully impersonates a legal identity
 288 and position. In addition, because sybil nodes are deployed after the original nodes, the level of the
 289 battery in a sybil node will be at its maximum. Thus, it is clear that the energy value of a sybil node
 290 should be greater than that of a legitimate node. In terms of sybil attack detection, it can be observed
 291

292 that a multi-level detection mechanism is more effective and efficient.

293

294 4.2. Energy Consumption

295 Energy is an important factor in WSNs because of its limited availability in sensor nodes.
 296 When fixed batteries are used, the energies of the sensor nodes should provide an effective basis for
 297 sybil detection. In the ETS approach, no detection system is applied at the CM level, detection and
 298 aggregation mechanisms are applied at the CH level, and at the BS level, only detection is applied.
 299 Figure 5 shows the amounts of energy consumed by the CMs, CHs, and BS in a clustered WSN with
 300 two clusters in the case of a sybil attack on one of the cluster heads. The results show that the BS,
 301 CHs, and CMs consume similar amounts of energy.

302

Figure 5. Amounts of energy consumed at different levels.

303 4.3. Communication Overhead Analysis and Comparison

304 The communication overhead is defined as the total number of packets forwarded by the nodes
 305 in the WSN. To evaluate the communication overhead under full-load conditions in an ETS network,
 306 the network is assumed to consist of m cluster heads. Each cluster contains n nodes, including the
 307 head. The other $(n-1)$ nodes forward messages, each of which must pass through the cluster head.
 308 Therefore, the maximum communication overhead C_{max} for the entire clustered WSN is calculated as
 309 in Equation 13:

$$C_{max} = m * C_{intra} + C_{inter} \quad (13)$$

310 where C_{intra} includes the communication of each CM with its CH and other CMs (if there is
 311 interaction among the CMs) and C_{inter} includes the communication of each CH with the BS and other
 312 CHs (if there is interaction among the CHs). Table 2 shows the communication overheads for various
 313 trust management methods in a large-scale clustered WSN.

314

Table 2. Communication overheads for ETS, LDTS [18], and GTMS [22].

Model	Communication Overhead
ETS	$m(n-1) + m$
LDTS [18]	$2m[(n-2)(n-1) + n] + 2(m-1)^2 + 2m$
GTMS [22]	$2m[n(n-1)n + (m-1)]$

315 Figure 6 shows the communication overheads for various attack detection approaches in terms of
 316 the number of packets forwarded by the nodes. This figure represents the performance in a network
 317 consisting of 10,000 nodes with different numbers of clusters. It is observed that the ETS method
 318 shows better performance compared with the LDTS [18] and GTMS [22] methods because it does not
 319 require recommendations or feedback from other nodes. Therefore, the results show that the ETS
 320 sybil detection system is highly suitable for large-scale WSNs.

Figure 6. Communication overhead in a network consisting of 10,000 nodes.

321

322 4.4. Memory Overhead Analysis and Comparison

323 Memory is one of the critical resources in sensor nodes. In the ETS approach, each entity must
 324 maintain a record or database. Each CM maintains a small database, as shown in Figure 7. Therefore,
 325 the ETS storage requirement at each CM is 8 bytes and is not affected by the cluster size.

The BS and every CH also must each maintain a database, as shown in Figure 8. The size of each

Node ID (bytes)	Position (bytes)	Energy (bytes)
2	2	4

Figure 7. Memory overhead at each CM.

326

327 record is $(4+2\Delta t)$, where Δt represents the length of the timing window. Therefore, the ETS memory
 328 requirement at each CH is $(8 + ((8 + 2\Delta t)(n - 1)))$, and that at the base station is $((8 + 2\Delta t)m)$. The
 329 size of the database stored by a CH depends on the cluster size and the length of the timing window.
 330 Furthermore, the size of the database stored by the BS depends on the number of clusters and the

length of the timing window. The memory overhead for the detection of sybil attacks using the ETS approach is illustrated in Figure 9.

Node ID (bytes)	Position (bytes)	Energy (bytes)	History (bytes)
2	2	4	$2 * \Delta t$

Figure 8. Memory overhead at each CH and the BS.

332

Figure 9. Memory consumed by the ETS approach.

The total memory required to implement the ETS approach for the detection of sybil attacks was calculated and compared with the memory required to implement the LDTS [18] and GTMS [22] approaches for attack detection in WSNs. For the same clustering topology, all clusters are assumed to be of equal size. The formulas for the memory requirements of the three trust systems, namely, ETS, LDTS [18], and GTMS [22], are given in Table 3, where m represents the number of clusters in the network and n represents the number of CMs in each cluster, including the CH.

339

Table 3. Analysis and comparison of storage requirements for ETS, LDTS [18], and GTMS [22].

Model	CM	CH
ETS	8	$8 + (8 + 2\Delta t)(n - 1)$
LDTS [18]	$7(n - 1)$	$7(m - 1) + 0.5m(n - 1)^2$
GTMS [22]	$(n - 1)(4 + 4\Delta t)$	$(m + n - 2)(4 + 4\Delta t)$

The results presented in Figures 10 and 11 are for a clustered WSN consisting of 1000 sensor nodes and for a timing window Δt equal to 5. As Figure 10 illustrates, ETS consumes less memory than the LDTS [18] and GTMS [22] schemes at both the CM and CH levels. At the CM level, the ETS approach must maintain a record of 8 bytes in each CM, independent of the cluster size. For LDTS, each CM must maintain $(7(n - 1))$ bytes; therefore, the amount of memory consumed depends on the cluster size. For GTMS, each CM maintains a database that depends on the size of the timing window, and the amount of memory consumed increases as the number of clusters increases. At the CH level, ETS consumes less memory with an increasing number of clusters. These results indicate

347

348 that the ETS approach is more suitable for large-scale WSNs with small clusters. For example, if the
 349 network consists of 100 clusters with an average size of 10 nodes, then the ETS scheme consumes 170
 350 bytes of memory. However, the LDTS approach consumes less memory as the number of clusters
 351 increases, whereas the memory consumption of the GTMS approach increases linearly as the number
 352 of clusters increases. Hence, all three schemes are suitable for large-scale WSNs, but ETS exhibits
 353 better performance.

354

Figure 10. Memory overhead at each CM in a network of 1,000 nodes.

Figure 11. Memory overhead at each CH in a network of 1,000 nodes.

355 5. Conclusion and Future Work

356 In this work, we propose a lightweight trust mechanism for detecting sybil attacks in clustered
 357 WSNs. Considering the nature of sybil attacks, we introduce a multi-level detection mechanism in a
 358 hierarchical WSN topology. ID and position verification is applied at each level, and then, a trust
 359 system is applied based on an energy threshold. Furthermore, the utilization of an aggregation
 360 mechanism and the elimination of the exchange of feedback and recommendations among nodes
 361 greatly improve the system efficiency while reducing the memory and communication overhead
 362 required to implement the proposed ETS approach. Thus, less energy consumption is required.

363 The results of the presented performance evaluation show that ETS can effectively detect sybil
364 attacks in WSNs. Moreover, an analysis of the proposed ETS approach indicates that the proposed
365 system is lightweight in terms of memory and communication overhead compared with other trust
366 mechanisms. Future work will investigate the validity of applying the ETS scheme in dynamic
367 networks such as mobile WSNs and MANETs. Furthermore, the detection ability of ETS for other
368 kinds of attacks will be evaluated.

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